

Synthesis and biological significance of 2-mercaptobenzoxazole derivatives

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Abstract : Several 2-aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-4-oxothiazolidines **4**, and 2-aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-5-arylidene-4-oxothiazolidines **5** have been synthesized by the appropriate methods and evaluated for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Streptococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhimurium*; antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium heterosporium* and *Rizopus oryzae* and antiinflammatory activity against the carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method in albino rats. In the primary screening some of the products displayed acceptable biological activity. The structure of the synthesized compounds has been established on the basis of their spectral and microanalytical data.

Keywords : Mercaptobenzoxazole, biological activity.

2-Mercaptobenzoxazole and their derivatives are known to possess several biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiinflammatory, insecticidal and herbicidal¹. 4-Oxo-thiazolidines have also played an important role as analgesic², anti-HIV, antitubercular³, anthelmintic⁴, dye-stuffs, fluorescent and as a photosensitizer. The incorporation of 4-oxothiazolidine and their 5-arylidene moieties in 2-mercaptobenzoxazole framework has been found to enhance the activity. Hence in the present study position 2 in the 2-mercaptobenzoxazole moiety having a thiol (-SH) group was used as the target for chemical modification (Scheme 1). These observations promoted us to synthesise the titled compounds (**1-5**) as per Scheme 1 with a view to evaluate their antibacterial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory activities.

2-Mercaptobenzoxazole with ethyl chloroacetate and anhydrous K₂CO₃ in the presence of dry acetone was refluxed on water bath to give ethyl-2-(mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetate (**1**), ($\nu_{\max}$ 1721, >C=O of ester; δ 1.22 and 4.12, CH₂ and CH₃ of COOCH₂CH₃; 4.39, S-CH₂). The compound (**1**) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in methanol to yield 2-acetylhydrazinomercaptobenzoxazole (**2**), ($\nu_{\max}$ 3458, 3360, 3318, NHNH₂; δ 4.78, NH₂; 7.88, CONH). The compound (**2**) was treated with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid in ethanol to give 2-mercaptobenzoxazoloacetamidyl arylidene (**3**), ($\nu_{\max}$ 1548, NHN=CH; δ 4.92, -N=CH) which when

refluxed with mercaptoacetic acid in THF with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl₂ gave 2-aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-4-oxo-thiazolidines (**4**), ($\nu_{\max}$ 1718, >C=O cyclic; 2965, S-CH₂; 2980, N-CH-S; δ 3.25, N-CH-Ar; 4.45, S-CH₂). The compound (**4**) on treatment with various aromatic aldehydes (benzaldehyde/nitro/chloro/methoxy benzaldehydes) in dioxane in the presence of C₂H₅ONa to give 2-aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-5-arylidene-4-oxothiazolidines (**5**), ($\nu_{\max}$ 1625, >C=CH-Ar; δ 5.16, >C=CH-Ar) (Table 1). All the compounds synthesized were characterized by their elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

Biological activity :

The compounds **4a-j** and **5a-j** were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* (*Ec*), *Shigella dysenteriae* (*Sd*), *Streptococcus aureus* (*Sa*) and *Salmonella typhimurium* (*St*). The following compounds showed maximum activity against the bacteria (in parenthesis) : **4f**, **5e**, **5g** (*Ec*); **4f**, **5f**, **5g** (*Sd*); **4d**, **4g**, **5e**, **5g** (*Sa*); **4e**, **4f**, **5f**, **5g** (*St*) respectively. Antifungal activity of these compounds against *Aspergillus niger* (*An*), *Candida albicans* (*Ca*), *Fusarium heterosporium* (*Fh*) and *Rizopus oryzae* (*Ro*) were also tested. The following compounds displayed significant activity against the fungi (in parenthesis) : **4f**, **4g** (*Ca*); **5g** (*Fh*); **5e**, **5f**, **5g** (*Ro*) respectively. The same compounds were also tested for their anti-inflammatory activity. The compounds **4g** (48.64%),

Table 1. Characterisation data of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	Ar ¹	Ar ²	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	Mol. formula	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
4a	C ₆ H ₅	-	78	110-112	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	55.98 (56.10)	3.84 (3.89)	10.81 (10.90)
4b	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	-	79	120-122	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	50.12 (50.23)	3.04 (3.25)	12.93 (13.02)
4c	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	-	81	120-121	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	50.12 (50.23)	3.20 (3.25)	13.00 (13.02)
4d	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	-	74	125-128	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	49.98 (50.23)	3.03 (3.25)	13.01 (13.02)
4e	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	-	84	108-109	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	51.39 (51.55)	3.31 (3.35)	10.01 (10.02)
4f	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	-	80	112-114	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	51.43 (51.55)	3.32 (3.35)	9.98 (10.02)
4g	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	-	82	118-119	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl	51.48 (51.55)	3.33 (3.35)	10.00 (10.02)
4h	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	-	83	115-116	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	54.83 (54.93)	4.07 (4.09)	10.08 (10.12)
4i	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	-	75	112-114	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	54.87 (54.93)	4.03 (4.09)	10.10 (10.12)
4j	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	-	78	116-117	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	54.88 (54.93)	4.08 (4.09)	10.07 (10.12)
5a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	84	112-114	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	63.39 (63.42)	3.97 (4.09)	8.79 (8.87)
5b	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	80	122-123	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₇ S ₂	53.20 (53.28)	3.00 (3.01)	12.39 (12.43)
5c	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	82	125-127	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₇ S ₂	52.23 (53.28)	2.95 (3.01)	12.35 (12.43)
5d	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	78	126-128	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₇ S ₂	53.21 (53.28)	2.98 (3.01)	12.41 (12.43)
5e	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	79	108-110	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	55.40 (55.45)	3.09 (3.14)	7.71 (7.76)
5f	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	81	112-114	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	55.39 (55.45)	3.12 (3.14)	7.72 (7.76)
5g	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	73	118-119	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	55.42 (55.45)	3.08 (3.14)	7.74 (7.76)
5h	2-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	79	119-121	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	60.75 (60.78)	4.29 (4.31)	7.78 (7.87)
5i	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	81	112-114	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	60.69 (60.78)	4.27 (4.31)	7.85 (7.87)
5j	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	84	118-119	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	60.74 (60.78)	4.30 (4.31)	7.85 (7.87)

5f (43.25%) and 5g (45.94%) showed reasonable activity while 4e (32.43%), 4f (35.43%), 5e (35.13%) displayed moderate antiinflammatory activity.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillary tube method. IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc on a

where Ar¹ and Ar² = -C₆H₅/2,3,4-NO₂C₆H₄/2,3,4-ClC₆H₄/2,3,4-OCH₃C₆H₄
 Scheme 1

Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer ($\nu_{\max}$ in cm^{-1}) and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX 300-spectrometer in CDCl₃ at 200 MHz on δ scale using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC on silica gel 'G' plates.

Ethyl-2-(mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetate (1) : Equimolar solution of 2-mercaptobenzoxazole (25 g, 0.17 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (20.17 g, 0.17 mol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (22.84 g, 0.17 mol) in dry acetone (125 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about 12 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was recrystallized from chloroform to give compound 1, 55.09 g (81%), m.p. 87–89° (Found : C, 55.53; H, 4.48; N, 5.87. C₁₁H₁₁NO₃S requires : C, 55.69; H, 4.65; N, 5.91%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1582, 1560, 1542, 1238, 1090 (benzoxazole with aromatic ring), 1721 (>C=O of ester), 2912, 2872, 1430 and 712 (CH₂ and CH₃), 710 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); δ 7.33–7.56 (4H, m, Ar-H), 1.22 (3H, t, *J* 7.00 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.12 (2H, q, *J* 7.00 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.39 (2H, s, S-CH₂).

2-Acetyl hydrazinomercaptobenzoxazole (2) : Equimolar solution of ethyl-2-(mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetate (1; 20 g, 0.085 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (4.27 g, 0.085 mol) in methanol (120 ml) was refluxed for about 5 h on a steam bath. After cooling the resulting solid was filtered. The product was recrystallised from ethanol to give

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j against various bacteria at different concentrations (ppm)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. dysenteriae</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>S. typhimurium</i>	
	25	50	25	50	25	50	25	50
4a	++	+	+	++	++	++	++	+++
4b	++	++	++	+	+	++	+++	++
4c	++	+	+	++	++	++	++	++
4d	+++	++	++	++	+++	+++	+	++
4e	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	+++	++++
4f	+++	+++	+++	++++	++	+++	+++	+++
4g	+++	++	++	+++	+++	+++	++	++++
4h	++	+	+	++	++	+	++	++
4i	++	+	++	++	+	++	++	++
4j	+	++	++	+	++	+++	+	++
5a	++	+	++	+	++	++	++	++
5b	++	++	+	+	++	+++	+++	++
5c	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
5d	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
5e	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++	++	++
5f	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	+++	++++
5g	+++	+++	++++	++++	+++	++++	+++	+++
5h	++	++	+	+	++	++	+++	++
5i	++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++	++
5j	++	+++	+	++	++	++	+++	+++
SM	+++	++++	++++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

SM = Streptomycin (standard drug); inhibition diameter in mm; (-) not effective; (+) 3–5 mm; (++) 5–12 mm; (+++) 12–24 mm; (++++) 24–30 mm.

Table 3. Antifungal activity of the compounds **4a-j** and **5a-j** against various fungi at different concentrations (ppm)

Compd.	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>C. albicans</i>			<i>F. heterosporium</i>			<i>R. oryzae</i>		
	10	50	100	10	50	100	10	50	100	10	50	100
4a	+	+	++	-	-	++	-	+	+	++	+	++
4b	++	++	+	++	++	+	+	++	++	++	+	+
4c	+	++	++	+	+++	++	+	++	++	++	+	++
4d	+	++	++	++	++	+	+	++	++	++	+	++
4e	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	++	+++
4f	+	++	++	++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	+	+++	+++
4g	++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
4h	+	+	++	+	++	+++	++	++	++	-	-	++
4i	+	+	+	++	++	++	+	++	++	-	+	+
4j	+	++	+	++	++	++	+++	+	++	++	++	+
5a	+	+	++	+	+	+	++	+	+++	+	++	++
5b	++	++	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	++	+++	++
5c	+	++	++	++	+++	++	++	++	+	++	+	++
5d	++	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++	++	+++	+++
5e	++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5f	++	++	++	++	++	+++	++	++	++	+++	+++	++++
5g	+	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
5h	+	+	+	-	-	+	++	++	++	++	++	++
5i	+	++	++	-	+	++	+	+	+	+	+	++
5j	+	+	++	+	++	++	+	++	++	++	++	++
GF	++	+++	++++	++	+++	++++	++	+++	+++	++	+++	++++

GF=Griseofulvin (standard drug); inhibition diameter in mm; (-) not effective; (+) 10–14 mm; (++) 14–20 mm; (+++) 20–25 mm; (++++) 25–29 mm.

compound **2**, 17.96 g (74%), m.p. 184–186° (Found : C, 48.25; H, 4.01; N, 18.71. $C_9H_9N_3O_2S$ requires : C, 48.43; H, 4.04; N, 18.84%); ν_{max} 1585, 1568, 1545, 1240, 1085 (benzoxazole with aromatic ring), 3458, 3360, 3318 ($-NHNH_2$), 1672 ($>C=O$, amido), 712 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); δ 7.88 (1H, s, CONH), 7.35–7.60 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.78 (2H, bs, NH_2) and 4.58 (2H, s, S- CH_2).

2-Mercaptobenzoxazoloacetamidyl arylidenes (3a) : Equimolar solution of 2-acetyl hydrazinomercaptobenzoxazole (**2**; 2.5 g, 0.012 mol), benzaldehyde (1.19 g, 0.012 mol) with two or three drops of glacial acetic acid in ethanol was refluxed on a steam bath for about 3 h. The solvent was removed and the product thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol to afford compound **3a**, 3.10 g (84%), m.p. 110–112° (Found : C, 61.68; H, 4.13; N, 13.42. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3O_2S$ requires : C, 61.74; H, 4.19; N, 13.50%); ν_{max} 1590, 1570, 1548, 1246 and 1088 (benzoxazole with aromatic ring), 1678 ($>C=O$, amido), 715 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); δ 7.25–7.55 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.92 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.12 (1H, s, CONH), 4.45 (2H, s, S- CH_2).

Other compounds (**3b-j**) were prepared similarly by reacting compound **2** with various aromatic aldehydes.

2-Aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-4-oxothiazolidines (4a) : Equimolar solution of 2-mercaptobenzoxazolo acetamidyl arylidene (**3a**; 2.0 g, 0.0065 mol) in THF (50 ml) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.59 g, 0.0065 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ was refluxed for about 8 h on a steam bath. The solvent was removed and the product was recrystallised from ethanol to give compound **4a**, 2.025 g (78%), m.p. 110–112° (Found : C, 55.98; H, 3.84; N, 10.81. $C_{18}H_{15}N_3O_3S_2$ requires : C, 56.10; H, 3.89; N, 10.90%); ν_{max} 1600, 1580, 1550, 1250 and 1080 (benzoxazole with aromatic ring), 2980 (N–CH–S), 2965 (S– CH_2), 1718 ($>C=O$, cyclic), 1672 ($>C=O$, amido), 718 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); δ 8.58 (1H, s, CO–NH), 7.30–7.55 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.45 (2H, s, S- CH_2) 3.69 (2H, s, CH_2CO) and 3.25 (1H, s, N–CH–Ar).

Other compounds (**4b-j**) were prepared by using (**3b-j**). Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

Table 4. Antiinflammatory activity of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	Dose	Before Carrageenan administration	Volume of paw (ml)					Total increase in paw volume after 5 h	Percent inhibition
			after drug administration (mean $\pm$ SE)						
			0 h	1 h	2 h	3 h	4 h		
4a	50	0.61 $\pm$ 0.04	0.70 $\pm$ 0.02	0.81 $\pm$ 0.02	0.86 $\pm$ 0.03	0.93 $\pm$ 0.02	0.97 $\pm$ 0.03	0.36 $\pm$ 0.02	2.70
4b	50	0.62 $\pm$ 0.03	0.68 $\pm$ 0.01	0.78 $\pm$ 0.02	0.83 $\pm$ 0.04	0.91 $\pm$ 0.02	0.96 $\pm$ 0.03	0.34 $\pm$ 0.00	8.10
4c	50	0.62 $\pm$ 0.02	0.69 $\pm$ 0.01	0.74 $\pm$ 0.03	0.81 $\pm$ 0.02	0.87 $\pm$ 0.02	0.92 $\pm$ 0.02	0.30 $\pm$ 0.00	18.91
4d	50	0.60 $\pm$ 0.03	0.67 $\pm$ 0.03	0.72 $\pm$ 0.04	0.76 $\pm$ 0.02	0.80 $\pm$ 0.01	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.29 $\pm$ 0.02	21.62
4e	50	0.64 $\pm$ 0.04	0.67 $\pm$ 0.03	0.69 $\pm$ 0.02	0.73 $\pm$ 0.03	0.81 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.25 $\pm$ 0.00	32.43
4f	50	0.67 $\pm$ 0.02	0.73 $\pm$ 0.03	0.78 $\pm$ 0.03	0.81 $\pm$ 0.03	0.85 $\pm$ 0.02	0.91 $\pm$ 0.02	0.24 $\pm$ 0.02	35.43
4g	50	0.62 $\pm$ 0.03	0.66 $\pm$ 0.02	0.71 $\pm$ 0.04	0.75 $\pm$ 0.02	0.79 $\pm$ 0.02	0.81 $\pm$ 0.02	0.19 $\pm$ 0.03	48.64
4h	50	0.64 $\pm$ 0.03	0.71 $\pm$ 0.03	0.79 $\pm$ 0.02	0.86 $\pm$ 0.03	0.91 $\pm$ 0.04	0.96 $\pm$ 0.02	0.32 $\pm$ 0.04	13.51
4i	50	0.67 $\pm$ 0.02	0.73 $\pm$ 0.04	0.80 $\pm$ 0.03	0.87 $\pm$ 0.03	0.90 $\pm$ 0.03	0.97 $\pm$ 0.01	0.30 $\pm$ 0.01	18.91
4j	50	0.60 $\pm$ 0.01	0.69 $\pm$ 0.02	0.78 $\pm$ 0.02	0.84 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.93 $\pm$ 0.01	0.33 $\pm$ 0.02	10.81
5a	50	0.60 $\pm$ 0.01	0.67 $\pm$ 0.02	0.72 $\pm$ 0.02	0.79 $\pm$ 0.01	0.86 $\pm$ 0.01	0.95 $\pm$ 0.03	0.35 $\pm$ 0.02	5.40
5b	50	0.55 $\pm$ 0.03	0.59 $\pm$ 0.02	0.66 $\pm$ 0.02	0.71 $\pm$ 0.03	0.79 $\pm$ 0.03	0.87 $\pm$ 0.02	0.32 $\pm$ 0.03	13.51
5c	50	0.63 $\pm$ 0.02	0.69 $\pm$ 0.04	0.77 $\pm$ 0.03	0.81 $\pm$ 0.01	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.93 $\pm$ 0.03	0.30 $\pm$ 0.04	18.91
5d	50	0.60 $\pm$ 0.03	0.67 $\pm$ 0.02	0.73 $\pm$ 0.03	0.76 $\pm$ 0.04	0.81 $\pm$ 0.01	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.29 $\pm$ 0.02	21.62
5e	50	0.66 $\pm$ 0.02	0.69 $\pm$ 0.04	0.74 $\pm$ 0.03	0.80 $\pm$ 0.02	0.86 $\pm$ 0.03	0.90 $\pm$ 0.02	0.24 $\pm$ 0.02	35.13
5f	50	0.59 $\pm$ 0.02	0.63 $\pm$ 0.04	0.69 $\pm$ 0.03	0.72 $\pm$ 0.01	0.75 $\pm$ 0.03	0.80 $\pm$ 0.02	0.21 $\pm$ 0.03	43.25
5g	50	0.71 $\pm$ 0.03	0.76 $\pm$ 0.03	0.80 $\pm$ 0.03	0.84 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.91 $\pm$ 0.04	0.20 $\pm$ 0.04	45.94
5h	50	0.54 $\pm$ 0.02	0.62 $\pm$ 0.03	0.69 $\pm$ 0.02	0.74 $\pm$ 0.04	0.80 $\pm$ 0.03	0.87 $\pm$ 0.03	0.33 $\pm$ 0.02	10.81
5i	50	0.66 $\pm$ 0.03	0.71 $\pm$ 0.03	0.79 $\pm$ 0.02	0.82 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.03	0.97 $\pm$ 0.02	0.31 $\pm$ 0.02	16.22
5j	50	0.64 $\pm$ 0.02	0.70 $\pm$ 0.03	0.78 $\pm$ 0.02	0.82 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.01	0.94 $\pm$ 0.02	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0	18.91
PB	50	0.76 $\pm$ 0.30	0.81 $\pm$ 0.02	0.82 $\pm$ 0.02	0.87 $\pm$ 0.03	0.89 $\pm$ 0.02	0.92 $\pm$ 0.02	0.16 $\pm$ 0.03	56.75
Control	50	0.62 $\pm$ 0.02	0.68 $\pm$ 0.03	0.76 $\pm$ 0.02	0.84 $\pm$ 0.03	0.90 $\pm$ 0.03	0.99 $\pm$ 0.02	0.37 $\pm$ 0.03	-

PB=Phenylbutazone (standard drug).

2-Aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-5-arylidene-4-oxo-thiazolidines (5): Equimolar solution of 2-aryl-3-[(2-mercaptobenzoxazolo)acetamidyl]-4-oxo-thiazolidene (4a; 1.5 g, 0.0005 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.425 g, 0.0005 mol) in dioxane (50 ml) in the presence of C_2H_5ONa were refluxed for about 3 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The resulting product was recrystallised from methanol to yield compound 5; 1.62 g (84%), m.p. 112–114° (Found: C, 63.39; H, 3.97; N, 8.79. $C_{25}H_{19}N_3O_3S_2$ requires: C, 63.42; H, 4.01; N, 8.87%); ν_{max} 2988 (N-CH-S), 1715 (>C=O, cyclic), 1678 (>C=O, cyclic), 1678 (>C=O, amido), 1625 (>C=CH-Ar), 1595, 1578, 1552, 1256 and 1082 (benzoxazole with aromatic ring), 718 cm^{-1} (C-S-C); δ 8.62 (1H, s, CO-NH), 7.28–7.59 (14H, m, Ar-H), 5.16 (1H, s, >C=CH-Ar), 4.42 (2H, s, S-CH₂) and 3.28

(1H, s, N-CH-Ar).

Other compounds (5b-j) were prepared by reacting (4b-j) with various aromatic aldehydes. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

Antibacterial (25 and 50 ppm concentrations) and antifungal (10, 50 and 100 ppm concentrations) activities of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j were assayed by filter paper disc method⁵. Streptomycin and Griseofulvin were used as standards for comparison to antibacterial and antifungal activity under the similar conditions. The antiinflammatory activity of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j were also tested using carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method⁶ at an oral dose of 50 mg/kg b.w. in albino rats (weighing 100–120 g). The percent inhibition of inflammation was calculated by applying Newbould formula⁷. Results of the activity are presented in Tables 2, 3 and 4.

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